

Optimised homogenisation methods of OFMSW, HORECA wastes and sewage sludges.

Deliverable 3.4

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PUBLISHABLE SUMMARY

Current European biowaste management is not yet aligned with the circular economy roadmap proposed by the European Commission. Across the EU, over 100 M tonnes of biowaste are produced every year, with management of this waste representing a cost as large as 143 billion euros. The reuse of this biowaste into valuable products could lead to a paradigmatic change in the waste management and will positively impact on the society from the economic, social and environmental point of view.

SCALIBUR, in order to accomplish with the Circular Economy principles, is focused on the valorisation of three different biowaste streams into high-added value products. The OFSMW will be convert into commodity chemical, bioplastics and biopesticides (WP4) by innovative enzymatic hydrolysis and submerged and solid-state fermentations, the HORECA wastes will be properly transform into proteins, lipids and chitin (WP5) by the action of insects (as the black soldier fly) and the sewage sludge will be converted into bioplastics and biopesticides (WP6) by bioelectrochemical technologies. Nevertheless, it has to be taken into account that homogenised biowastes should be obtained in order to achieve high efficiencies during the biowastes transformations.

The optimisation of the homogenization methods of the OFMSW, HORECA wastes and sewage sludge is different and has been evaluated individually. In the case of OFMSW, the separation of the organic fraction from the inorganic one should be done. Nevertheless, for HORECA wastes are characterised by the different nature of the components that conforms the whole stream so big efforts should be done in order to obtain an homogenise stream by grinding techniques in order to be able to carry out effectively analyses on such a poorly homogeneous sample to administer this stream of biowaste to rearing insects in the best way, while the sewage sludge should be studied in order to observe the proper treatments that should be developed in order to obtain a potential "fuel" for the production of the high-added value components by electrochemical technologies.

This report shows the biowaste pre-treatment and treatment lines for the homogenisation of the biowaste streams in the different Demo-sites (Madrid, Toledo and Emilia Romagna). In addition, innovative pre-

treatments that are already under study, and other innovative pre-treatments that will be developed in the next weeks, in the framework of SCALIBUR project are described.

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